

Prelude to the Localized Magnetism Semi-conductor Electron Excitation (LMSEE) Project

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Nanotechnology Localized Magnetism Semi-conductor Electron Excitation (LMSEE) makes use of electron excitation in semiconductors to produce practical dc power. The undoubtedly preeminent nature of an electron as a basic source of energy, how such energy can be practically harnessed from this subatomic particle of matter so can be usable to help address contemporary power needs out of clean, sustainable and environmentally friendly manner, depicting a strong contrast with recent mainstream energy sources and means. Mankind today favors clean energy technologies and is showing progress on global warming mitigation, carbon footprint reduction or elimination, net-zero emissions, energy efficiency, and the sustainability or preservation of the world's resources. The epitome of this work dealt with electrons, in materials at the nano-particle size or smaller that could generally exist in semiconductors, that can be induced to a behavior that will constitute motion, exploited for practical power generation applications and other innovative solutions to address real-world electricity requirement challenges, ushering a new era of renewable energy technologies. This conceived **new technology** will see fruition through the **LMSEE Project** that focused on the **device** being initiated first for patent application and subsequent production, **seeking for funding** as of this writing, for further research and development, be a subject of scientific discussions, pave way for entrepreneurial insights and kindle business opportunities, or achieve commodity status for the common good.

1 About the Technology

One of the technologies proposed in the **paper** entitled **Break Electron - The Practical Electron Energy Manifesto** is about a nanotechnology direct current

power generation device using static electromagnetic field and semiconductors. For patent application stage as of this writing, the device would involve a technique that will be called Localized Magnetism Semi-conductor Electron Excitation (*LMSEE*) wherein materials are suitably selected and engineered such that electron excitation in the resulting semiconductor is achieved during encounter with incident EM field at the non-radioactive EM spectrum, though the same scheme is proposed to utilize EM radiation from radioactive sources in later works.

Previously unnoticed and untapped, the technologies forwarded in this work involve points tackled in the paper with the stated title (accessible in this url <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117258>) this author had written and published at the European Council for Nuclear Research (CERN) digital repository *Zenodo.org* that is also referenced at other online research publishing platforms such as in *ResearchGate.net* (<https://bit.ly/jgp-electronenergy-rsgate-primer>) or at that posted in innovations repository site *LeadingEdgeOnly.com* (<https://lnkd.in/gFyxcjNM> and <https://bit.ly/leo-lmseepimer>).

2 The Future of Renewable Energy

The electron, in materials at the nano-particle size or smaller that could generally exist in semiconductors, can be induced to a behavior that will constitute motion that can be exploited for practical power generation applications and other innovative solutions to address real-world challenges, ushering a new era of renewable energy technologies. This conceived **new technology** will see fruition in the *LMSEE Project* that focused on the device being sought for patent registration.

3 Applicable to Everything that Needs Electricity

The mentioned **paper** provides the building block of the localized magnetism semi-conductor electron excitation (LMSEE) method and device proposed in the *LMSEE Project*. The technique can be applied to significantly improving performance of present solar power generation photovoltaic (PV) cells, semiconductors, and the like. The technology can be the building block of new portable power devices as applied in mobile phones, wearable gadgets and medical devices, electric-powered tools and equipment, heating/cooling systems, power generation units, electric vehicles (EV), unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV), drones (aerial and marine), terrestrial and extraterrestrial or deep space satellites, deep space navigation, and others.

4 Key Benefits, Commercial Applications and Opportunities

The technology can practically find wide applications in mobile and portable power devices and gadgets, small to medium to large power generation systems in various industries such as in the production of wearable medical devices to outer space explorations.

Mass production in various forms and market - power source for portable and mobile devices, small to medium to large power generation systems, as applied in various industries ranging from wearable medical devices to outer space explorations to commodity applications.

The **patent** can benefit from manufacturing and commodity or mass production licensing of the technology. Manufacturing licensing for mass production in various forms and market – power source for portable and mobile devices, small to medium to large power generation systems, applications covers various industries ranging from wearable medical devices to outer space explorations to commodity status can create revenue opportunities.

5 Other Relevant Topics

The **paper** also discussed other practical energy sources influenced by the movement of electrons - electromagnetic radiation (EMR) that can be converted into electric power by tuning at nature's resonant frequencies, heat as an EMR at the infrared EM spectrum (wherein waste heat can be converted into electricity using Seebeck Effect TEG), EMR as energy source in plants' growth process, etc. More of such proposed technologies are included in the **paper** as well as other related articles for the **LMSEE Project** can be found at <https://bit.ly/lmseepimer> and <https://lnkd.in/gThXs8jg>.

6 The Innovator

Joel G. Paramo is an electrical engineer with over two decades of professional experience, handled various power generation industry roles covering power plant project management, operation and maintenance, construction, commissioning, and testing. His faith as a member and a church locale officer of the **Iglesia Ni Cristo (Church of Christ)** essentially involve imploring **God's** guidance in the pursuit of knowledge instrumental in further serving **Him**, our **Heavenly Father**, and **Christ Jesus** (see also <https://incmedia.org>). As such, recent interests cover renewable energy research and development, sustainable design and technological and energy innovations. Particular present endeavor involve the **LMSEE Project** tackled in this **article**. A **B4X** software developer, find **Joel's** profile and professional interests on **Facebook**, in **LinkedIn**, and **published projects, papers, and energy**

innovations, respectively in *Zenodo.org* and *LeadingEdgeOnly.com*.

7 References

This technical primer can be accessed from the **LMSEE prelude page** (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10202265>). References used in the cited **paper** (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10117258>) of the **LMSEE Project** (<https://zenodo.org/communities/thelmseeproject>) are shown in the next pages.

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